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NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF CASING TREATMENT EFFECTIVENESS FOR BLI-LIKE DISTORTION AT VARIOUS SKEWED ANGLES

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ABSTRACT

Boundary Layer Ingestion is a critical technology for future high-efficiency aircraft, but the inherent inlet distortion poses significant challenges to fan stability. This paper numerically investigates the effectiveness of an arc-shaped slotted casing treatment with varying skew angles to increase the stall margin in a transonic fan under BLI-like conditions. The results show that under distorted inflow, stall is initiated by the amplification of the tip leakage vortex within the low-momentum region, leading to severe passage blockage at the distortion sector's exit. The casing treatment enhances stability by inducing a dual momentum exchange mechanism: it suctions low-momentum fluid downstream of the passage shock and re-injects it upstream, effectively suppressing the blockage. A key finding is the direct correlation between the slot skew angle and the stability enhancement; stall margin improvement (SMI) increased from a marginal 0.62% for a 35° angle to a substantial 30.72% for a 55° angle. This performance difference is attributed to the treatment's ability to accommodate the increasing radial flow angle of the suction flow as the fan is throttled. The study concludes that a larger skew angle provides a more robust match with the flow dynamics near stall, offering a highly effective design strategy to improve the stability of fans operating under severe inlet distortion.

Keywords: Casing Treatment; Inlet Distortion; Boundary Layer Ingestion (BLI); Transonic Fan; Stability Enhancement.

NOMENCLATURE

C_p Static pressure coefficient
 $C_{p,t}$ Total pressure coefficient

$C_{v,c}$ Chordwise velocity coefficient
 $C_{v,r}$ Radial velocity coefficient
 $C_{v,t}$ Tangential velocity coefficient
 $C_{v,z}$ Axial velocity coefficient
DC(140) Circumferential total pressure distortion index
 \bar{m} Normalized mass flow rate
 P Static pressure
 P^* Total pressure
 q_m^* Characteristic mass flow rate
 Tr_{tip} Passive scalar tracer for tip leakage flow
 U_{mid} Blade tip velocity at 50% span
 V Average velocity at fan inlet
 V_r Radial velocity
 V_t Tangential velocity
 V_z Axial velocity
 α_γ Radial flow angle of the suction flow
 γ Geometric slot skew angle
 ρ Standard air density
 ϕ_{bleed} Net bleed flow coefficient
 Ω_{v+} Area at slot base with positive radial velocity
ASCT Arc-shaped Slotted Casing Treatment
BLI Boundary Layer Ingestion
SC Solid Casing
SM Stall Margin
SMI Stall Margin Improvement
TLV Tip Leakage Vortex

1 INTRODUCTION

Against the global backdrop of climate change and the drive for sustainable development, the international aviation industry faces unprecedented pressure to reduce emissions, necessitating disruptive technologies to lower fuel consumption, noise, and harmful pollutants [1]. Boundary Layer Ingestion (BLI) has emerged as a revolutionary propulsion-airframe integration concept to meet this demand [2–4]. The core principle involves ingesting the low-speed boundary layer airflow, which is typically attached to the airframe surface and generates drag, into the engine. By re-energizing this low-momentum flow, BLI technology not only reduces the aircraft’s wake momentum deficit and overall drag but also significantly enhances propulsive efficiency by lowering the inlet flow velocity. Theoretical studies and conceptual designs indicate that aircraft employing BLI could achieve double-digit fuel savings [5], positioning it as a key technological pathway toward future green aviation and inspiring novel aircraft configurations such as the blended-wing-body (BWB) [6].

However, while promising substantial benefits, BLI technology also introduces unprecedented challenges to the stable operation of the fan [7]. The ingestion of the low-energy boundary layer from the fuselage surface forces the fan to operate continuously in a highly nonuniform and distorted inflow environment [8]. This BLI-induced distortion severely degrades the fan’s aerodynamic performance and drastically erodes its inherent stall margin, rendering traditional stability design criteria inadequate, demanding robust new solutions [9–11].

It is well-established that stall in modern, highly loaded transonic fans often originates from the breakdown of complex flow structures in the tip region, primarily the tip leakage vortex (TLV) [10, 12]. Consequently, effective control of the tip flow field is paramount for enhancing stability. Casing treatments (CT) have proven to be a highly effective passive flow control technique specifically targeting these tip-initiated stall phenomena [13, 14]. Among various designs [15, 16], axial skewed slots are particularly potent [17, 18], as they can generate a powerful momentum exchange by suctioning low-energy fluid and re-injecting it to re-energize the main flow [19, 20].

Despite the proven potential of axial skewed slots, their effectiveness is critically dependent on geometric parameters [21], with the skew angle being one of the most influential [22]. A significant knowledge gap persists in the systematic, parametric investigation of this angle, especially concerning its impact on performance under the highly three-dimensional and distorted flow fields characteristic of BLI. The precise physical mechanisms governing stall suppression in this context are not yet fully understood. This is particularly evident in the context of complex inlet conditions, such as the BLI inlet.

Therefore, this paper presents a systematic numerical investigation on a transonic fan to thoroughly explore the stability enhancement effectiveness of an Arc-shaped Skewed Casing Treatment (ASCT) under BLI-like distortion conditions. The core of

this work is to systematically vary the skew angle of the treatment slots to analyze the influence of this critical parameter on the fan’s stall margin recovery. The findings of this study will not only elucidate the interaction mechanism between the casing treatment and the main flow in a distorted environment but also provide a crucial theoretical basis and design reference for the development of high-efficiency, low-loss casing treatments for future BLI propulsion systems.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Object and Casing Treatment Geometry

The subject of this investigation is a single transonic fan rotor, specifically designed for a distributed Boundary Layer Ingestion (BLI) aircraft configuration. The fan is characterized by a design pressure ratio of 1.4, an adiabatic efficiency of 0.89, and a tip tangential velocity of 390 m/s.

To systematically investigate the influence of the skew angle on stability enhancement, three distinct Arc-shaped Skewed Casing Treatment (ASCT) configurations were developed for this fan. While key geometric parameters such as the number of slots, slot depth, overlap length (L_{CTO}), and total slot length (L_{CT}) were held constant, the slot skew angle (γ) was systematically varied. The three angles chosen were $\gamma = 35^\circ$, $\gamma = 45^\circ$, and $\gamma = 55^\circ$. For clarity, these configurations are hereafter referred to as CT35, CT45, and CT55, respectively. A schematic illustrating the geometric parameters of the arc-shaped slots is provided in Figure 1.

2.2 Computational Setups

The numerical simulations were conducted using a suite of commercial software. Structured hexahedral meshes were generated using NUMECA Autogrid, while the steady and unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS/URANS) equations were solved using Ansys CFX. The Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model was selected for turbulence closure. To ensure accurate resolution of the boundary layer, the near-wall mesh was refined to maintain a Y^+ value below 5 on all solid surfaces.

Considering the significant computational expense of unsteady simulations, a hybrid simulation strategy was adopted. The overall fan performance characteristics were obtained from steady-state RANS simulations. Subsequently, high-fidelity URANS simulations were performed at critical operating points to facilitate a detailed analysis of the complex flow field phenomena. For steady calculations, the frozen rotor approach was employed at the rotor-stator interface. In the unsteady simulations, a sliding mesh interface was used to accurately capture the transient interaction between the rotor and stationary components. The unsteady simulations utilized a dual time-stepping scheme; the physical timestep was set to 1/15 of the time required for a rotor blade to pass over a single treatment slot, which corresponds to 1440 timesteps per full rotor revolution.

FIGURE 1: STRUCTURE OF THE ARC-SHAPED SLOTS.

Figure 2 presents a meridional view of the computational domain. The total pressure ($P_{\text{atm}}^* = 101325 \text{ Pa}$) and total temperature ($T_{\text{atm}}^* = 288.15 \text{ K}$), corresponding to standard sea-level atmospheric conditions, were prescribed at the domain inlet. The inlet parameter measurement section station 1 is located at twice the chord length ahead of the rotor leading edge. The outlet parameter measurement section station 2 is located at twice the chord length behind the rotor trailing edge.

To simulate the effects of boundary layer ingestion, a BLI-like inlet distortion was imposed by introducing a static pressure loss distribution function at an interface between two stationary domains situated upstream of the rotor. A momentum source term corresponding to a pressure loss (P_{loss}) was applied at the interface plane. The pressure loss was defined by the following equation:

$$P_{\text{loss}} = C_p(r_n) \cdot \frac{\bar{q}_{\text{ref}}}{q_0} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{q}_{ref} is the area-averaged dynamic head at the interface. The function is dependent on the normalized spatial coordinate r_n , which is defined to represent the normalized distance from the bottom of the casing, corresponding to the center of the BLI profile. By this definition, $r_n = 0$ at the point of maximum pressure deficit, and it increases radially outwards.

The loss coefficient $C_p(r_n)$ was formulated as a piecewise

polynomial to approximate a typical boundary layer profile:

$$C_p(r_n) = \begin{cases} c_1 r_n^2 + c_2 r_n + c_3 & \text{for } 0.3 \leq r_n < 0.9 \\ c_4 r_n + c_5 & \text{for } r_n < 0.3 \\ 0 & \text{for } r_n \geq 0.9 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The dimensionless coefficients (c_1 through c_5) were carefully calibrated to produce a smooth, continuous profile that matches a desired distortion intensity and shape. This formulation effectively creates a quadratic pressure loss profile in the main shear region of the boundary layer and a linear profile in the near-wall sublayer, with no loss applied in the freestream ($r_n \geq 0.9$).

This approach provides a computationally efficient and robust means of simulating a stable and representative inlet distortion, allowing for a systematic analysis of the fan's performance across its entire operating range.

At the outlet boundary, a static pressure was prescribed alongside a radial equilibrium equation. The complete characteristic curve of the fan was generated by progressively increasing the back pressure, starting from an initial value of $P_0 = 101325 \text{ Pa}$.

For configurations featuring the casing treatment, a coupled buffer zone mesh was generated, as illustrated in Figure 3. This buffer zone, with a radial thickness equivalent to approximately 5% of the rotor tip clearance, established a frozen rotor/sliding mesh interface with the rotor tip. The buffer zone mesh and the treatment slot mesh were generated conformally, thereby eliminating the need for a numerical interface between them and ensuring seamless data transfer.

FIGURE 2: MERIDIONAL VIEW OF COMPUTATIONAL DOMAINS.

A grid independence study was conducted using single-passage steady simulations to validate the mesh resolution. As

FIGURE 3: COMPUTATIONAL MESH SCHEME OF THE CASING TREATMENT SLOT.

illustrated in Figure 4, which plots the fan's pressure ratio and efficiency at the peak efficiency point against varying grid densities, the results demonstrate that grid-independent solutions are achieved when the single-passage mesh count reaches approximately 4.1×10^5 cells. Consequently, a high-fidelity mesh configuration of 4.1×10^5 cells per passage, totaling 7.8×10^6 cells for the full annulus, was adopted for all subsequent investigations to ensure both accuracy and computational efficiency.

FIGURE 4: GRID INDEPENDENCE VERIFICATION RESULTS.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of Inlet Distortion on Stability

The total pressure contour at the fan inlet and the total pressure distribution at different radial heights, as obtained from numerical simulations, are shown in Fig. 5. The simulation effectively captures the total pressure deficit characteristic of boundary layer ingestion. At the peak efficiency point, the corresponding circumferential total pressure distortion index, DC(140), is 14.5%. The total and static pressure coefficients used in this paper are defined as:

$$C_{p,t} = \frac{P^* - P_1^*}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_{mid}^2} \quad (3)$$

$$C_p = \frac{P - P_1^*}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_{mid}^2} \quad (4)$$

where P^* is the total pressure, P is the static pressure, P_1^* is the average total pressure at station 1, ρ is the standard air density, and U_{mid} is the blade tip velocity at 50% span. The circumferential total pressure distortion index is defined as:

$$DC(140) = \frac{P_1^* - P_W^*}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V_1^2} \quad (5)$$

where P_W^* is the average total pressure within the 140° distorted region, and ρV_1^2 is the average dynamic pressure at station 1.

This study conducted numerical simulations of the fan under the aforementioned BLI-like distortion. For comparison, a uniform inflow case was also simulated. Figure 6 presents the fan performance characteristics under both uniform and distorted inflow, while Table 1 summarizes the performance metrics. As seen, the fan's stall margin experiences a significant drop under distorted inflow. As this fan was specifically designed to tolerate BLI, featuring an elliptical leading edge and wide-chord blades, its performance under uniform inflow is slightly compromised to enhance its tolerance to inlet distortion. Consequently, its efficiency does not decrease significantly under distorted inflow.

To investigate the underlying reasons for the stall margin degradation under distorted inflow, a detailed analysis of the unsteady flow field at the near-stall operating point ($\dot{m} = 0.86$ for distorted inflow) was conducted.

First, the inlet distortion induces significant circumferential and radial non-uniformities in the flow field upstream of the fan (at two chord lengths ahead of the rotor), as shown in Figure 7. The definitions for tangential velocity coefficient $C_{v,t}$ and axial velocity coefficient $C_{v,z}$ are:

$$C_{v,t} = \frac{V_t}{U_{mid}}, \quad C_{v,z} = \frac{V_z}{U_{mid}} \quad (6)$$

where V_t is the tangential velocity and V_z is the axial velocity. The lower total pressure in the distorted region causes fluid from

TABLE 1: EFFECT OF INLET DISTORTION ON FAN PERFORMANCE.

Condition	Peak Efficiency	Stall Margin (SM)
Uniform	90.1%	30.53%
Distorted	89.9%	21.37%
Change	-0.2%	-9.16%

(a) Contour plot of total pressure coefficient.

(b) Unwrapped total pressure coefficient profiles at different spanwise locations.

FIGURE 5: TOTAL PRESSURE COEFFICIENT PROFILE AT THE FAN INLET (STATION 1).

the high-pressure, clean-inflow region to migrate towards it, generating a tangential velocity coefficient ($C_{v,t}$). Concurrently, the axial velocity coefficient ($C_{v,z}$) distribution exhibits a more complex pattern. In the tip region near the casing, the ingestion of the low-momentum boundary layer leads to a significantly lower axial velocity within the distorted sector compared to the clean sector. Conversely, the situation is reversed near the hub. This is attributed to the stagnation effect of the inlet cone, which, com-

FIGURE 6: FAN PERFORMANCE MAPS UNDER UNIFORM AND DISTORTED INLET CONDITIONS.

binated with the low total pressure in the distorted sector, creates a strong circumferential pressure gradient near the hub. This gradient drives fluid toward the distorted sector, increasing the local mass flow and thus resulting in a higher axial velocity at the hub within the distorted region.

These changes in the inlet velocity triangle directly alter the relative inlet flow angle at the blade's leading edge. Figure 8 illustrates the circumferential distribution of the relative inlet flow angle at different spanwise locations. The variation in flow angle is strongly correlated with the axial velocity distribution. At 95% span, the sharp decrease in axial velocity within the distorted sector leads to a dramatic increase in the relative inlet flow angle. At 50% span, in the core flow region, the flow parameters change minimally, and the flow angle remains nearly constant. At 10% span, due to the anomalous increase in axial velocity, the relative inlet flow angle decreases within the distorted sector.

It should be noted that while the distortion induces a tangential velocity, its absolute magnitude is small, and its impact on the relative inlet flow angle is negligible compared to the dominant effect of the axial velocity variation.

FIGURE 7: CONTOUR PLOTS OF AXIAL VELOCITY ($C_{v,z}$), TANGENTIAL VELOCITY ($C_{v,t}$), AND STATIC PRESSURE (C_p) COEFFICIENTS UPSTREAM OF THE ROTOR.

A direct comparison with the uniform inflow case at their respective near-stall points ($\dot{m} = 0.86$ for distorted inflow, $\dot{m} = 0.84$ for uniform inflow) reveals that the distortion precipitates a non-synchronous stall development. To visualize the transport of the tip leakage flow, a passive scalar (Tr_{tip}) was introduced in the tip clearance gap. The results, shown in Fig. 9, illustrate the dramatic effect of the distortion. As the blades enter the distorted sector, they encounter a higher angle of attack, which intensifies the tip leakage flow. The Tip Leakage Vortex (TLV) grows in strength and size, eventually spilling forward of the adjacent blade's leading edge just before exiting the distortion, causing severe passage blockage. In contrast, the near-stall condition for uniform inflow shows a strong but contained TLV.

As the blades rotate out of the distortion, the high-momentum fluid of the clean inflow periodically disrupts and suppresses this localized blockage. However, stall is triggered when the periodic breakdown of the TLV coverage, which occurs as the rotor blades exit the distorted sector, is no longer sufficient to suppress the blockage effect of TLV. Therefore, the reduction

FIGURE 8: UNWRAPPED RELATIVE INLET FLOW ANGLE PROFILE AT DIFFERENT SPANWISE LOCATIONS.

in stall margin is not due to a uniform degradation of the flow field but rather a localized, periodic intensification of the TLV that dictates the stability limit.

3.2 Stability Enhancement Mechanism of the Casing Treatment

The effectiveness of an arc-shaped slot casing treatment with a 55° skew angle (CT55) was evaluated under the distorted inflow condition. As shown in the performance map in Fig. 10, the CT55 configuration significantly enhances the fan's stall margin compared to the solid casing (SC) baseline.

The stability enhancement is achieved through a dual momentum exchange mechanism. Figure 11 compares the chordwise velocity coefficient ($C_{v,c}$) at 95% span for the SC and CT55 cases. The CT55 effectively suppresses the severe blockage region observed in the SC case by injecting high-momentum fluid upstream of the passage shock. This is further clarified in Fig. 12, which shows a detailed view of both chordwise and radial velocity ($C_{v,r}$). The treatment suctions low-momentum fluid downstream of the shock (positive $C_{v,r}$) and injects it upstream of the shock (negative $C_{v,r}$), re-energizing the main flow and preventing stall development.

Figure 12 shows a magnified view of the chordwise and radial velocity at the exit of the distorted sector for the CT55 configuration at a mass flow rate of $\dot{m} = 0.86$. The radial velocity coefficient is defined as:

$$C_{v,r} = \frac{V_r}{U_{mid}} \quad (7)$$

where V_r is the radial velocity, positive from hub to casing. From the figure, it is clear that the high chordwise velocity upstream

FIGURE 9: UNWRAPPED CONTOUR PLOTS OF RELATIVE MACH NUMBER AND PASSIVE SCALAR (Tr_{tip}) AT 99% SPAN.

of the shock corresponds to a high negative radial velocity, while the low chordwise velocity downstream of the shock corresponds to a high positive radial velocity. This indicates that the casing treatment suctions the low-velocity fluid from the passage downstream of the shock and injects it upstream of the shock. This mechanism avoids the continuous accumulation of low-momentum fluid and, at the same time, increases the momentum of the incoming main flow, thereby suppressing stall development.

The dual action of suction and injection by the casing treatment within the distorted sector is a key factor in its ability to suppress stall and enhance stability. This effect itself is driven by the local recirculation flow induced by the casing treatment. Therefore, this study calculated the distribution of the net bleed flow coefficient, ϕ_{bleed} , along the circumference, defined as:

$$\phi_{bleed} = \frac{\iint_{\Omega_{v+}} \rho V_r d\sigma}{q_m^*} \quad (8)$$

where Ω_{v+} is the target circumferential region at the base of the

FIGURE 10: FAN PERFORMANCE MAP UNDER DISTORTED INLET CONDITION FOR SOLID CASING AND CT55 CONFIGURATIONS.

treatment slots where the radial velocity is positive, and q_m^* is a characteristic mass flow rate. In the passage-averaged calculation, q_m^* is 1/18 of the total physical mass flow (18 being the number of rotor blades). Simultaneously, the radial flow angle of the suction flow within the Ω_{v+} region is defined as α_γ . Figure 13 shows the net suction flow coefficient ϕ_{bleed} , the passage-averaged chordwise velocity coefficient $C_{v,c}$ at 95% span, and the suction flow radial angle α_γ for the CT55 configuration at different mass flow rates. It can be seen that at a given flow rate, the suction flow increases as the rotor passes through the distorted sector, reaching a maximum upon exit. Across different flow rates, the lower the fan's flow rate, the higher the suction flow from the treatment. For the chordwise velocity at 95% span, at a given flow rate, it gradually decreases as the rotor enters the distorted sector and recovers upon exit. As the flow rate decreases and the fan approaches stall, the region of low chordwise velocity expands circumferentially. The suction flow's radial angle increases as the fan's flow rate decreases and also circumferentially in regions of lower chordwise velocity.

FIGURE 11: UNWRAPPED CONTOUR PLOT OF CHORDWISE VELOCITY COEFFICIENT AT 95% SPAN.

FIGURE 12: DETAILED VELOCITY COMPONENTS CONTOUR FOR CT55 NEAR THE EXIT OF THE DISTORTED SECTOR ($\bar{m} = 0.86$).

From the analysis above, the stall process of the rotor can be summarized as follows: as the fan’s flow rate decreases, the blockage accumulated in the distorted sector becomes increasingly severe, and the circumferential extent of the blockage re-

gion expands. Concurrently, the suction flow rate and the radial flow angle of the casing treatment increase. When the local recirculation of the treatment is insufficient to suppress its circumferential development, stall eventually occurs. A key factor affecting the treatment’s suction capability is the radial flow angle of the suction flow. As seen at the near-stall point ($\bar{m} = 0.74$), the radial flow angle of the suction flow has already far exceeded the treatment’s design skew angle of 55° .

3.3 Effect of Skew Angle on Stability Enhancement

To further evaluate the influence of the slot skew angle on the stall margin enhancement, the fan’s performance was characterized with three distinct casing treatment configurations. As presented in Figure 14, these configurations, designated CT35, CT45, and CT55, feature slot skew angles of 35° , 45° , and 55° , respectively. Table 2 summarizes the performance of the fan with different casing configurations. Within the scope of this study, the Stall Margin Improvement (SMI) is minimal for CT35, only about 0.62% compared to the solid casing, while larger skew angles yield more significant margin improvements.

TABLE 2: EFFECT OF CASING CONFIGURATION ON FAN PERFORMANCE UNDER INLET DISTORTION.

Config.	Peak Eff.	SM (%)	SMI (%)
SC	89.9%	21.45	-
CT35	89.4%	25.07	0.62
CT45	89.6%	42.63	21.18
CT55	89.5%	52.17	30.72

The preceding analysis indicates that the local recirculation induced by the casing treatment at the rotor tip is a crucial factor in improving the tip blockage, and the ability of the treatment to induce this local recirculation is key to its stability enhancement. Figure 16 compares the net suction mass flow, chordwise velocity at 95% span, and the radial angle of the suction flow for the three casing treatments as the flow rate varies. For CT35, which has the weakest stability enhancement capability, the radial angle of its suction flow increases most rapidly as the flow rate decreases. At $\bar{m} = 0.93$, the suction flow’s radial angle in the clean sector already exceeds its design angle. This makes it least effective at suppressing the blockage generated within the distorted sector, and its net suction flow shows limited improvement at near-stall conditions. For CT45, its ability to induce local flow at the tip is stronger than CT35 but slightly weaker than

FIGURE 13: CHANNEL-AVERAGED NET BLEED FLOW COEFFICIENT, CHORDWISE VELOCITY, AND RADIAL FLOW ANGLE FOR THE CT55 CONFIGURATION AT DIFFERENT MASS FLOW RATES.

FIGURE 14: FAN PERFORMANCE MAPS FOR SC, CT35, CT45, AND CT55 CONFIGURATIONS UNDER DISTORTED INLET.

FIGURE 15: VELOCITY FIELD IN THE NET BLEED REGION NEAR THE DISTORTED SECTOR EXIT, COMPARING FLOW ANGLE (α_γ) TO SLOT ANGLE (γ).

CT55. Comparing the operating points of CT45 at $\bar{m} = 0.91$ and $\bar{m} = 0.81$ with those of CT55 at $\bar{m} = 0.91$ and $\bar{m} = 0.82$, it is evident that at similar high flow rates, the net suction flow of CT45 and CT55 is very close, and the suction flow radial angle of CT45

at the same phase location is slightly higher than that of CT55. However, as the flow rate further decreases, CT45 encounters a problem when faced with a continuously increasing suction flow radial angle; it cannot provide a larger suction flow, which leads to its inability to suppress the circumferential development of the

FIGURE 16: CHANNEL-AVERAGED BLEED CHARACTERISTICS (ϕ_{bleed} , $C_{v,c}$, AND α_γ) FOR CT35, CT45, AND CT55 CONFIGURATIONS.

low-speed blockage, causing stall.

Figure 15 shows the velocity field at the base of the treatment slots in the net suction region near the exit of the distorted sector for the three configurations at their respective near-stall points. It can be clearly seen that for CT35, the suction flow's radial angle α_γ is significantly greater than the treatment's skew angle γ , indicating that the treatment is nearing failure. For the CT45 configuration, α_γ is approximately equal to γ . For the CT55 configuration, α_γ is still much smaller than γ , indicating that for these two configurations, there is still some margin for an increase in α_γ .

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study investigated the stall characteristics of a transonic fan under BLI-like inlet distortion and evaluated the effectiveness of an arc-shaped slotted casing treatment with varying skew angles for stability enhancement. The key findings are as follows:

1. Under the influence of the BLI-like inlet distortion, the fan's stall mechanism is localized and periodic. Low-momentum fluid, originating from the Tip Leakage Vortex (TLV), progressively accumulates as the rotor blades pass through the distorted sector. This accumulation culminates in severe passage blockage at the interface where the blades exit the distorted region, making this location the critical point for instability.
2. The Arc-Shaped Casing Treatment (ASCT) enhances stability by implementing a dual momentum replenishment mechanism. The slots suction low-momentum fluid from the post-shock region of the blade passage, which directly mitigates the development of flow blockage. This captured fluid is then re-injected into the pre-shock region, energizing the core flow. This combined action of suction and injection effectively suppresses the localized stall trigger and extends the fan's stable operating range.

3. A direct correlation exists between the slot skew angle and the magnitude of stability enhancement: a larger skew angle yields a more significant improvement in stall margin. This is because as the fan's flow rate is reduced, the increasing tangential velocity of the flow entering the slots causes the resultant radial flow angle of the suction flow to increase. Treatments with a smaller skew angle are the first to encounter a mismatch, where the required radial flow angle exceeds the geometric design angle of the slots. This mismatch compromises the internal recirculation flow, diminishing the treatment's ability to suppress rotating stall and ultimately leading to stall. In contrast, a larger skew angle maintains an effective alignment with the radial flow dynamics even at lower mass flow rates, thus providing a more robust stability enhancement.

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